

METAPHOR IN LITERATURE. ("ANIMAL FARM" BY GEORGE ORWELL)**Mushtariy begim Hoshimova****Fergana**<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20116490>

Annotation: The article touches upon metaphor and using it in literature, such as prose. As we know, the word is considered the most important tool in literature due to its importance to make the meaning of your work clearer and more impressive. This article is dedicated to using this term in one of different genres and finding out reasons or aim of writers to use metaphor in their work. So as to do analysis, "Animal farm" by George Orwell can be a good example as it is about animal at the farm.

The novelty of the article is finding different metaphors in one work, and analyze what purpose from using.

Key words: Metaphor, simile, auxiliary, formative affixes, subordinate clause, dominant clause, synecdoche

A **metaphor** is a figure of speech that, for rhetorical effect, directly refers to one thing by mentioning another. It may provide (or obscure) clarity or identify hidden similarities between two ideas. Metaphors are often compared with other types of figurative language, such as antithesis, hyperbole, metonymy and simile. One of the most commonly cited examples of a metaphor in English literature comes from the "*All the world's a stage*" monologue from *As You Like It*:

*All the world's a stage,
And all the men and women merely players;
They have their exits and their entrances ...*
(William Shakespeare, *As You Like It*) [7]

This quotation expresses a metaphor because the world is not literally a stage. By asserting that the world is a stage, Shakespeare uses points of comparison between the world and a stage to convey an understanding about the mechanics of the world and the behavior of the people within it. [1]

Naming one word after another on the basis of the similarity or even difference of two things is called metaphor. In Greek "metaphore" means transfer which serves to reinforce the meaning of the word. When this term is used one word takes the name of something that has another similar property according to a smell, size, feature, shape, even smell and taste.

When the meaning of one word is transferred to another one, the basic or common feature of the former is not lost. Using metaphor can be met mostly in literature. Because with the help of it, author can express his ideas with emotive and clear way. That is why it is considered that writer and metaphore is friends.

Metaphore is one of the most important literary tool which compare two different thing in an unexpected way in our mind.

Metaphor in literature

In different books it said that, for literature metaphor is necessary like drop of water. Because, most authors or writers are accustomed to use this kind of term so as to give color to their work or make it more impressive and attractive to their readers. Sometimes the metaphore that they use can be tranlator of their basic idea, and when it is take it from text, it will lose its meaning.

There some purpose to use metaphore in literature

- ✓ **Metaphors can make prose more muscular or imagery more vivid**
 - ✓ **Writers frequently turn to metaphors to describe people in unexpected ways**
 - ✓ **Metaphors can help frame abstract concepts in ways that readers can easily grasp**
- [3]

If you are going to use any metaphor you should know why you are using, can differentiate from other types of literary devices, and be able to influence to your readers through impressive ideas. Because, giving such ideas that clear, precise or expressing more ideas by the help of less vocabulary is a key in order to avoid encountering misunderstanding while they are reading your work. As an example, one of the most popular novel “Animal farm” by George Orwell has been taken. In this literary work, through the speech of different animals, the author has used metaphor in a professional way.

Metaphoric ananlysis of “Animal farm”

1. “All through that summer the work of the farm went **clockwork**. The animals were happy as they had never conceived it possible to be. Every mouthful of food was an **acute positive pleasure**, now that it was truly their own food, produced by themselves and for themselves, not doled out to them by a grudging master.”

In this sentence metaphor is used so as to **make prose more muscular or imagery more vivid meaning that author tried to describe situation more expressive with the help of literary device. This metaphor means everything at farm went smoothly and precise time (from 8 to 5)**

In the next sentence, words “acute” and “positive” are used with word “pleasure” in order to express the feeling with an exaggerated way. In most literary works, we may encounter this kind situation as it is considered an important tool to attract the reader to that written work.

Beasts of England, beasts of Ireland,

Hearken to my **joyful tidings**

Of **the golden future time**.

Soon or late **the day is coming**,

Tyrant Man shall be overthrown,

In the poem that is given in the novel, we can see wide range of metaphors even in every line. With a help of it, writer tries to create vivid imagery that transcends literal meanings, creates atmosphere that can be easier to understand for reader. Metaphorical phrase is considered as a key to create imagination, and the writer is able to convey emotions and impressions through metaphor. In the poem that is given in the novel, metaphor is used to support literary meaning of the work. There are more than two metaphors in a five lined poem, such as “**Joyful tidings**” and “**the golden future**”. These metaphors are one of the type of metaphor related its feature. Writer has used it **make prose more muscular or imagery more vivid, meaning to describe the situation clearer, understandable for readers. Besides that, here writer has tried to entertain and tickle the brain, metaphor examples sometimes compare two extremely unlike things.**

Another metaphoric example is “**The day is coming**”. As we know, verbs related to action is used for human or animals, not for non-movement items. But here we can see the author use metaphor to make is alive. And **metaphors can help frame abstract concepts in ways that readers can easily grasp.**

2. When Squealer went on to give further graphic details of Boxer's **death-bed**, the admirable care he had received, and the expensive medicines for which Napoleon had paid without a thought as to the cost, their last **doubts disappeared**. “Death-bed” (o’lim to’shagi) in this phrase, metaphor is used to exaggerate the meaning of the phrase. The word “Disappeared” is one the type of metaphor.

expressions to make the context more alive.

Conclusion

As noted above, through metaphor, two dissimilar or unrelated concepts are connected, unexpected analogies are made in order to attract the reader’s attention, and the writer of abstract and incomprehensible situations delivers to the reader through the same method.

In fiction, many writers sometimes use metaphoric color to exaggerate the ideas they want to express. The reason is that the works attract the reader with their artistic function.

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